

First and second derivative spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) using 2-acetylthiophene-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone

K. Hussain Reddy^{a*}, N. B. L. Prasad^b, T. S. Reddy^a and M. Syaji Rao^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

^bOil Technological Research Institute, JNTU, Anantapur-515 001, Andhra Pradesh, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, OU PG Center, Mirzapur-502 249 (Medak Dt.), Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract : The reagent, 2-acetylthiophene-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (ATPT) has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) in aqueous medium. The reagent gives intense colour reaction with copper(II) in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer medium. Maximum colour intensity observed in the pH range 3.0-6.0. First and second derivative methods have been developed for the determination of copper(II) in aqueous medium. First derivative spectrum of Cu-ATPT complex has maximum amplitude at 420 nm which is selected in analytical studies. On the other hand the second derivative spectrum of Cu-ATPT complex exhibits maximum amplitude at 410 nm (peak) and 455 nm (valley) and the zero cross at 485 nm. The amplitude at 410 nm is proportional to the amount of copper(II). Therefore, this wavelength is chosen in second derivative method.

Keywords : Derivative spectrophotometry, copper(II).

In continuation of our ongoing work on the analytical application of heterocyclic phenyl thiosemicarbazones¹, we report herein first and second derivative spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) using 2-acetylthiophene-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (ATPT). Derivative spectrophotometry is very useful technique since it decreases the interference of foreign ions and may be advantageously used for the selective determination of metal ions in natural samples.

Results and discussion

The reagent, 2-acetylthiophene-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone is easily prepared under reflux conditions^{1(b)}. Even dilute solution (0.001 M) of ATPT is stable for 12 h. In basic medium, the ligand presumably exists in enolic form and coordinates to copper(II) to give 1 : 2 (M : L) neutral complex.

Determination of copper(II) : Cu^{II} reacts with ATPT in acidic pHs to give yellow coloured complex at room temperature. The derivative amplitudes of the complex remains constant for 5 h in both orders. The peak heights are found to be constant in the pH range 3-6 both in first and second derivative methods. In both methods a 5-fold molar excess of reagent is found to be sufficient to achieve maximum peak amplitude. In first derivative spectrum a

peak is observed at, 410 nm while in second derivative spectrum both peak and valley are observed at 420 and 455 nm respectively. Standard and relative standard deviations of second derivative method are 0.0070 and 2.86 respectively in ten replicate determinations of 0.41 µg/ml of copper.

Derivative spectra of Cu-ATPT complex : The zero-order spectrum of copper complex with ATPT in the buffer solution of pH 4.0 is recorded in the wavelength region 350-600 nm against reagent blank (Fig. 1, curve b). The

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of (a) ATPT vs water blank and (b) Cu-ATPT complex vs ATPT blank. $[Cu^{II}] = 1.6 \times 10^{-6} M$, $[ATPT] = 5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, pH = 4.0.

complex shows maximum absorbance at 385 nm where the reagent blank has lower absorbance (curve a). From the zero-order spectrum, first and second derivative spectra are recorded (Fig. 2). The first derivative spectrum shows that the complex has maximum amplitude at 420 nm. Therefore, this wavelength is selected for further analytical studies. The second derivative exhibits a maximum amplitude at 410 nm (peak) and 455 nm (valley) and the zero cross at 485 nm. But at 410 nm, the amplitude is proportional to the amount of copper(II). Therefore this wavelength (410 nm) is chosen for further studies.

In derivative spectra of Cu-ATPT complex amplitudes are observed at higher wavelength i.e. 420 nm in the first derivative spectra and 410 nm in the second derivative spectra. As a result tolerance limits for foreign ions are increased for some anions and cations.

Individual calibration plots are constructed at 420 nm (first derivative) and 410 nm (second derivative) by plotting derivative amplitudes against the amounts of metal ions. The plots are linear obeying the relationship

$$A_{420} = 0.0146C - 0.0004$$

$$A_{410} = 0.0448C + 0.0165$$

in first and second derivative spectra respectively. The amplitude is proportional to the metal ion concentration in the ranges 0.102–0.918 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.20–1.02 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of copper(II) in the first and second derivative spectra respectively.

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of foreign ions has been investigated by adding different amounts of anions and cations to 0.40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of copper in solution. The colour is developed as described in the recommended procedure. An error of plus or minus 2% in the amplitude is considered tolerable. Tolerance limits of foreign in the determination of 0.41 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of copper in the first and second derivative methods respectively are as follows : iodide 1520, 1550; tartrate 1175, 1210; bromide 960, 950; sulphate 770, 780; phosphate 760, 750; nitrate 495, 510; bicarbonate 490, 490; carbonate 480, 480; acetate 470, 460; thiocyanate 465, 450; chloride 425, 450; citrate 380, 375; ascorbate 350, 350; cyanate 335, 330; fluoride 230, 230; iodate 75, 70; thiosulphate 45, 45; thiourea 30, 25; oxalate 7, 10; W^{VI} 2205, 2200; Ba^{II}

Fig. 2. (A) First derivative and (B) second derivative spectra of Cu-ATPT complex Conditions as in Fig. 1

1650, 1500; Sr^{II} 1050, 1050; Ca^{II} 480, 450; Al^{III} 320, 350; Mg^{II} 290, 310; Pb^{II} 250, 260; Cd^{II} 135, 150; Zr^{IV} 110, 110; Zn^{II} 80, 95; Co^{II} and Fe^{III} 70, 75; Ni^{II} 70, 70; Mn^{II} 65, 65; Sn^{II} 50, 50; Mo^{VI} 40, 45; Fe^{II} 20, 20; Ag^I 1.3, 13; V^V 5, 8 and Hg^{II} 2, 2.5 µg/ml. It is noticed that all the ions that do not interfere in the zero-order determination of copper(II) with ATPT also do not interfere in the first derivative spectrophotometric analysis. The tolerance limits of certain ions are higher than those in the zero-order determination of copper(II)^{1(b)} with ATPT. Mercury(II) and vanadium(V) which interfere in the zero-order are found to be tolerable up to 2 and 1 µg/ml respectively.

The foreign ions that do not interfere in the first derivative spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) with ATPT also do not interfere in the second derivative spectrophotometric analysis. Tolerance limit values for certain foreign ions are high in second derivative spectra. A 13 µg/ml of Ag^I, 7.6 µg/ml V^V and 2.5 mg/ml Hg^{II} do not interfere in the second derivative spectrophotometric determination of copper(II).

Analysis of edible oils and seeds :

Sample solutions of edible oils and seeds were prepared by following the procedure given in the literature². A 50 g of the sample (in the case of seeds it was finely grinded) was taken in a 500-ml conical flask containing 40 ml of concentrated HNO₃. The acidified sample was heated on a steam bath and shaken vigorously until a fine emulsion was formed. It was treated with 40 and 20 ml portions of 6% H₂O₂ and the extracts were collected in a beaker and evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in minimum amount of dil. HCl and transferred into a 50-ml standard flask quantitatively. The contents

were diluted to the mark with distilled water.

To 10 ml of buffer solution (pH, 4.0) , 1 ml of 0.1 M sodium fluoride, oil sample solution, 2.5 ml of DMF and 1 ml of 0.001 M reagent solution were added. The solution was diluted to the volume (25-ml) with distilled water and the absorbance was measured at 385 nm against reagent blank. The results are given in Table 1. A known quantity (1 µg/ml) of copper(II) were added to the sample and the amount of the metal ion was estimated as described above. The recovery data are incorporated in Table 1.

Experimental

Schimadzu 160A microcomputer based UV visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0-cm quartz cells were used for all absorbance and amplitude measurements in derivative spectrophotometry. An ELICO LI-120 Digital pH meter was used in pH adjustments. All the reagents used were of A.R. grade unless otherwise specified. All solutions were prepared with distilled water. Stock solution (0.01 M) of copper(II) was prepared by dissolving requisite quantity of cupric sulphate in 250-ml distilled water. The stock solution was standardized³ titrimetrically using standard EDTA solution and diluted to obtain working solutions of metal ion.

The reagent, 2-acetylthiophene-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (ATPT) was prepared by simple condensation of one mole of 2-acetylthiophene with one mole of thiosemicarbazide. The synthesis and characterization of ATPT using UV-visible, IR, NMR and mass spectra were reported earlier^{1(b)}.

Recommended procedures :

An aliquot of the solution containing copper(II) in the optimum concentration range i.e. 0.1–0.51 µg ml⁻¹ or ppm, 10 ml of NaOAc-AcOH buffer solution of pH 4.0,

Table 1. Determination and recovery of copper in edible oils and oil seed using second derivative method

Sample	Copper found ^a (µg/ml)		Recovery	
	Present	AAS	Present	AAS
	method	method	method	method
Groundnut seed	4.38	4.45	98.5	102.6
Ground nut oil	0.58	0.60	97.9	99.5
Sesame seed	11.51	11.75	101.5	99.2
Sunflower oil	0.64	0.65	96.4	101.6
Hydrogenated vegetable oil	0.97	0.98	101.5	101.8

^aAverage of three determinations.

2.5 ml of DMF and 2 ml of 0.001 M ATPT solution were mixed in 25-ml standard flask and the mixture was diluted to the mark with distilled water. Absorption and derivative spectra (first and second) of Cu-ATPT complex were recorded in the wavelength range 350–600 nm against reagent blank. The zero-order spectrum shows absorption maximum at 385 nm. Plots between derivative amplitude and the amount of copper(II) were prepared.

First derivative method : The calibration plot was linear and obeys the relationship, $A_{420} = 0.0146C - 0.0004$. However, the linearity is critically dependent on the wavelength.

Second derivative method : The calibration plot was linear and obeys the relationship, $A_{410} = 0.0448C + 0.0165$. The linearity is not critically dependent on the wavelength.

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